

**European network to promote
grazing and to support grazing-
based farms on their economic and
ecologic performances as well as
on animal welfare**

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of G4AE is to strengthen grassland-based farmers' capacities in optimising and promoting the grazing of ruminants on European grassland agroecosystems. The economic, ecological, societal and animal health values are the underlying rationale of this goal. G4AE promotes them through multi-actor collaboration, co-creation and knowledge-sharing within and between partner farm networks and national agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKISs). On a policy level, G4AE aims particularly at strengthening actors of the grazing value chain to anchor grassland-based agriculture in the EU's commitment to the Green Deal and the implementation of the Farm to Fork strategy.

This task addressed this aim by reviewing the European landscape of value chain actors of the private sector related to grazing. Specifically, it identified agri-food product labels and labelling approaches which recognize the production of grassland-/grazing-based food and thus certify such product lines.

2 Survey

A review process was initiated to identify product labels across the eight member states and also Switzerland. All partners were asked to reach out to their national network and scout for labels or labelling approaches and collect information on the following criteria. The following structure has been proposed by GLZ and accepted by the entire consortium:

- Type of label institution
 - Private, Public, Trusteeship, Foundation, Other
- Mission of the label in the framework of G4AE's five agroecological principles
- Year of initiation
- Website
- Contact data
- Requirements for grazing practices
- Additional requirements
- Number of farmers certified under the label
- Expected benefits for beneficiaries
- Products targeted
 - Dairy, Beef, Other

3 Results

In total, 40 label or label initiatives from eleven countries were identified:

Table 1: Grazing labels from eleven European countries identified in a scouting process.

Country	Total
Austria	1
EU-wide	2
France	2
Germany	4
Ireland	3
Italy	3
Netherlands	4
Portugal	6
Romania	5
Spain	1
Sweden	4
Switzerland	5

A summary is given in Table 2 below. A more detailed table including grazing requirements and expected benefits is included in the [Appendix \(Table 3\)](#).

Table 2: Results of inventoried label initiatives which recognize grassland-based agri-food products, performed by all G4AE member states.

Country	Logo	Name	Type	URL
Austria		ARGE Heumilch	Private	heumilch.at
EU-wide		Bioland	Private	www.bioland.de
		Heumilch/Haymilk/Latte	?	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/le

		fieno/Lait de foin/Leche de heno		gal-content/DE/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32016R0304
France		Association Lait de pâturage	Association	https://www.maitres-laitiers.fr/fr/lait-de-paturage-sans-ogm
			Association	
		Pâtures et papilles	Association	https://paturesetpapilles.fr/le-label/
Germany		PRO WEIDELAND Deutsche Weidecharta GmbH	Private	https://proweideland.eu
		Hochland SE	Private	https://www.hochland-group.com/en/sustainability/weidemilch.htm
		Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V.	Non-profit association	https://www.tierschutzlabel.info/fileadmin/users/redakteur/redakteur_upload/Milchkuehe/2023/RL_Milchkuehe_2023.pdf

		Milchwerke Schwaben eG	Private	https://www.milchwerkeschwaben.de/axel-weidemilch
Ireland		The National Dairy Council	Private	https://ndc.ie/ndc-guarantee-trademark/
		Ornua	Cooperative marketing	https://www.ornua.com/
		Bord Bia - The Irish Food Board	Public	<p>"https://www.bordbia.ie/globalassets/bordbia2020/farmers-growers/grass-fed-standard/grass-fed-dairy-rev01-final.pdf</p> <p>https://www.bordbia.ie/globalassets/bordbia2020/farmers-growers/grass-fed-standard/grass-fed-beef-standard-</p>

				revision-02-draft1.pdf"
Italy		DELEG- Deutschnonsberger & Ultentaler Landwirtschaftliche Erzeugergenossenschaft	Association of producers	https://www.deleg.it/laugenrind/
		BIO BEEF vom Südtiroler Bauernhof / Dal maso sudtirolese	Association of producers	https://www.bio-beef.it/de/
		Latte Nobile/ANFOSC - Associazione Nazionale Formaggi sotto il cielo	Private	https://www.anfosco.it/
Netherlands		Stichting Weidegang	Foundation	https://www.weidemelk.nl
		Stichting Milieukeur	Foundation	https://www.planetproof.eu/producten/melk/
		Stichting Beter Leven keurmerk	Foundation	https://beterleven.dierenbescherming.nl/over-de-dieren/alle-dieren/melkkoeien/
		Beter voor Koe, Natuur en Boer (zuivel)	private	https://www.ah.nl/over-ah/duurzaamheid/onze-ketens/zuivel

<p>Portugal</p>		<p>Carne Barrosã PDO Carnalentejana PDO</p>	<p>Producer Organisatio n</p>	<p>www.carnebarrosa.com</p>
		<p>Carne Mertolenga PDO</p>	<p>Producer Organisatio n</p>	<p>https://carnalentejana.pt/</p>
		<p>TERRA NOSTRA Leite de Pastagem Vacas Felizes</p>	<p>Private</p>	<p>https://terra-nostra.pt/programa-leite-de-vacas-felizes/</p>
		<p>UNILEITE Leite de Pastagem</p>	<p>Private</p>	<p>https://unileite.com/</p>
		<p>MILHAFRE Leite de Pastagem</p>	<p>Private</p>	<p>https://www.milhafredosacores.pt/product_categories/leite-milhafre-dos-acores/</p>
<p>Romania</p>		<p>Asociația pentru promovarea produselor tradiționale de pe Valea Gurghiului</p>	<p>Private</p>	<p>https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/produse-traditionale/caiet-de-sarcini-</p>

				telemea-ibanesti.pdf
		Asociația Producătorilor de Telemea de Sibiu	Private	https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/2018/telemea-de-sibiu/caiet-sarcini-telemea-de-sibiu-2018.pdf
		PRODUS MONTAN	Association of producers	https://produsmontan.ro/
		Asociația Producătorilor "Cașcavalul De Săveni"	Public	https://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/2017/caiet-sarcini-cascaval-saveni-2017-.pdf
Spain		De Yerba	?	https://www.lacarnedepasto.com/
Sweden		Swedish Pasture Beef and Lamb association	NGO	www.naturbete.se
		KRAV	Private	https://www.krav.se/
		Fran Sverige	Public	https://jordbrukverket.se/djur/personal-inom-

				djurens-halso-- och- sjukvard/veterin ara- forfattningshan dboken#LDjursk ydd
	?	Haghultskossorna	Private	https://hagshult.se/om-oss/
Switzerland		Fidelio - Biosuisse	?	fidelio Fidelio- Biofreiland AG & Fidelio Produkte AG Rohrerstrasse 118 5001 Aarau
		Bio - Weide - Beef	Private	https://igbioweidebeef.ch/index.php/de/
		KAG Freiland	?	https://www.kagfreiland.ch/
		Natura-Beef	?	https://mutterkuh.ch/de/natura-beef
		Natura-Veal	?	https://mutterkuh.ch/de/natura-veal

3.1 Planned Cross-border networking

Further, the project aims at linking these actors to the practitioners' and science communities. Thus, this task will feed into T5.4, and a label conference will be held.

4 Appendix

Table 3: Additional criteria and information collected for each label (raw data)

Name of Organisation	Year of start	Number of Farmers certified under this label	Products (dairy, beef, etc.)	Expected benefits and Beneficiary	Goals/Mission of Label in relation to the 5 Agroecological principles	Grazing requirements	Additional requirements
Heumilch		7000	Dairy		Utilizing local resources and nurturing diverse, perennial grasslands, enhances soil health, sequesters carbon, and contributes to soil fertility. Through timely and staggered mowing of meadows and pastures, Heumilch fosters a rich array of grasses and herbs. This approach supports pollination and provides essential habitats for a variety of species, promoting biodiversity. Cows under the Heumilch Label live in free-stall housing and/or have access to pastures. This ensures their well-being and natural behaviors.	At least 120 grazing days in case of tie-stall housing. No control element for loose housing stalls (see European implementing regulation).	Species-appropriate feeding. No fermented feed such as silage. GMO-free. Only European feed. Only feed without palm oil and without coconut fat are allowed. Farmers have to comply with special fertilizer regulations. The number of animals is limited is proportional to the farm area. At least 75% DM roughage. Milk delivery from 10 days after calving. Minimum waiting time of 3

								weeks between the application of manure and grazing.
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<p>Bioland</p>	<p>1971</p>	<p>9.000</p>	<p>Dairy & Meat and Meatproducts</p>		<p>see https://www.bioland.de/sieben-prinzipien, 7 Bioland principles: 1. Managing and working in a cycle; 2. Enhance soil fertility; 3. Keep animals species-appropriate; 4. Produce valuable food; 5. Enhance Biodiversity; 6. Conserve natural resources; 7. Ensuring people a future worth living</p>	<p>According to Bioland requirements: Cattle for breeding and beef should have the possibility of free movement throughout the whole year. Cattle above 12 months shall have access to pasture during vegetation period. The min. grazing area is 600 m² per livestock unit during the total vegetation period. In case of extremely wet or dry conditions the grazing can be suspended for a short term. Inspections of animal husbandry quality are conducted using criteria related to both husbandry practices and product outcomes, assessing animal well-being and production quality. BIOLAND provides guidelines with key checkpoints and evaluation factors. Contractual operations are</p>	<p>The private BIOLAND guidelines are constantly evolving by the Bioland Assembly of Delegates. Main focus since many years is a separate check on species-appropriate animal husbandry. Since 2022 Bioland requires a standard on Biodiversity on each farm.</p>
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						<p>inspected through a written questionnaire (operation report) and an annual on-site visit by an inspector. The visit results in an inspection report, and this process ensures compliance with BIOLAND's standards.</p>	
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Heumilch/Haymilk/Latt e fieno/Lait de foin/Leche de heno	2016		Dairy			Reference to the animals being fed fresh grass, legumes and forbs during the green-feeding period (growing season = (?)). No control element about grazing implementation and duration.	No fermented feed such as silage. GMO-free. Farmers have to comply with special fertilizer regulations. At least 75% forages. Milk delivery from 10 days after calving. Minimum waiting time of 3 weeks between the application of manure and grazing.
Association Lait de pâturage	2017		Dairy			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cows are allowed to graze for at least 6 hours per day for an average of 150 days per year (with a mandated minimum of 120 days). • The grazing area should be at least 0.1 ares per day at least 0.1 are per day. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processors set up a special collection circuit
Pâtures et papilles	2022	25	Dairy & Meat and Meatproducts		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve animal welfare • Regenerate agricultural soils • Limit GHG emissions • Reduce energy consumption • Limit erosion, improve water quality • Support local economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum 240 grazing days/year • Animals are 100% grass fed • Organic production only • grasslands must rest for at least 2 months par year • grasslands must 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Silage (grass, maize) is forbidden at all times • Haylage is forbidden during lactation and fattening

						have more than 2 species	
PRO WEIDELAND Deutsche Weidecharta GmbH	2017	2020	Dairy & Meat and Meatproducts			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 120 days with six hours of grazing each day. • There must be 2,000 square meters of grassland per cow (of which at least 1,000 square meters must be pasture). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The animals' year-round freedom of movement must be guaranteed • ban on tethering • A scrub-scrub brush is available for the cows • Pasture milk is to be produced on the basis of GMO-free feed.

Hochland SE	2021		Dairy	<p>The most natural form of livestock farming: pro animal welfare and pro environment. The organisation is not an economic actor in this regard. It pursues the objective of reclassifying and promoting the numerous functions of grassland to reflect its diversity and significance. For the environmentally sustainable and nature-friendly use of pasture. With PRO WEIDELAND, these aspirations have been put into practice with a defining seal of approval for products from grass-fed livestock.</p>	<p>The PRO WEIDELAND label is awarded to dairy products whose raw ingredients have been sourced in a way that respects animal welfare and environmental protection. It may only be used by partners who are committed to pasture farming, which is more time- and labour-consuming but also more sustainable, and who meet our specific criteria.</p> <p>The content of the PRO WEIDELAND standards is based on the framework conditions and criteria, which are defined jointly by the multi-stakeholder community in our Weidecharta.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 120 days with six hours of grazing each day. • There must be 2,000 square meters of grassland per cow (of which at least 1,000 square meters must be pasture). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The animals' year-round freedom of movement must be guaranteed • ban on tethering • A scrub-scrub brush is available for the cows • Pasture milk is to be produced on the basis of GMO-free feed. <p>-When dehorning calves under six weeks of age (if practiced on the farm), administration of an effective analgesic for pain relief is mandatory. Participation in antibiotic monitoring and slaughter data collection with recording in a central database for the formation of indices is required. The implementation must take place from the year 2022</p>
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Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V.	2013		Dairy & Meat and Meatproducts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • animal welfare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • animal welfare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least six hours of grazing every day of the growing season • At least 1,000 square meters per cow must be pasture • installation of one drinking trough for every 4 ha of grazing land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obligation to attend training every two calendar years • Many regulations around animal welfare • GMO-free feed
Milchwerke Schwaben eG	2023		Dairy		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • animal welfare • regional production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 120 days with six hours of grazing each day • at least 1,000 square meters per cow must be pasture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pasture milk is to be produced on the basis of GMO-free feed • regional farms from Bavaria & Baden-Württemberg
The National Dairy Council	2009	18,000 dairy farmers	Dairy	The National Dairy Council (NDC) champions the role of sustainable, quality, pasture-based dairy production and its nutrition benefits in supporting healthier and more active living.	To be the world's most trusted exporter of sustainably driven and technically advanced high quality dairy products to customers worldwide.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No specific requirements. Products are more guaranteed Irish and locally produced and processed. 	

Ornua	2018	14,000 dairy farmers	Dairy	Ornua is a dairy co-operative which markets and sells dairy products on behalf of its members; Ireland’s dairy processors and, in turn, Irish dairy farmers.	Our cows enjoy a natural life, grazing outside for most of the year and are protected by high standards of animal welfare. As we grow, we must protect our low intensity, grass-fed family farming system and the health and wellbeing of our animals.	Our cows enjoy a natural life, grazing outside for most of the year and are protected by high standards of animal welfare.	
Bord Bia - The Irish Food Board	2020	50,000 farmers and over 100 meat processors	Dairy & Meat and Meatproducts	Developed by Bord Bia, the Irish Food Board, our Grass-Fed Standard is the world’s first independently verified standard that provides verifiable proof of the grass-fed status of each dairy herd. Therefore, it provides assurance for what we have long known to be true: grass is intrinsic to the quality of Irish dairy.	Bord Bia’s Grass-Fed Standard brings a data-based assurance that dairy is sourced from dairy herds that enjoy a diet that’s on average 95% grass and grass-based forage and graze in open pastures for an average of 240 days a year.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The minimum acceptable grass-fed figure for an individual herd to qualify as grass-fed is 90% on a fresh weight basis. • Animals must be permitted to graze outdoors on grass for a substantial part of year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Herds must be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - certified members of (SDAS) Sustainable Dairy Assurance Scheme in case of dairy Herds - members of the Sustainable Beef & Lamb Assurance Scheme in case of beef herds

DELEG- Deutschnonsberger & Ultentaler Landwirtschaftliche Erzeugergenossenschaf t	2004	60	Meat and Meatproducts		<p>The "LaugenRind" label follows a "zero kilometers" approach, minimizing transportation distances to promote a circular economy, reduce environmental impact, and utilize local resources. By fostering direct connections between farmers and consumers, it ensures fair prices for farmers and offers customers authentic, high-quality products. This integration strengthens local economic cycles, benefiting producers, restaurants, and retailers. Emphasizing distinct identity and quality, the label supports sustainable practices, reduces carbon emissions, and prioritizes ethical farming and social responsibility.</p>	<p>Weekly outdoor access must be ensured until the final fattening phase, in any case, outdoor access of at least 120 days (including grazing of alpine summer pastures). Animals with an age over 10 months must be let graze alpine summer pastures.</p>	<p>The calves must be born in South Tyrol with a traceable pedigree. Calves are reared with mother's milk, without any milk powder additives. Young animals must be bought within the first 14 days of life. Species-appropriate animal husbandry, ensuring movement and grazing. Concentrated feed must be GMO-free. Short transportation to slaughterhouses. The stall must not have fully slatted floors. Calves must have straw-covered floors.</p>
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<p>BIO BEEF vom Südtiroler Bauernhof / Dal maso sudtirolese</p>		<p>25</p>	<p>Meat and Meatproducts</p>		<p>The mission of "Bio-Beef" aligns with the 5 Agroecological principles by promoting organic farming, natural animal husbandry, and regional sustainability. South Tyrolean mountain farmers prioritize the animals' well-being with grazing in summer and free-housing stables in winter, ensuring appropriate feeding with fresh grass and farm's own hay. The compliance with the guidelines are regularly checked by control bodies "ABCert" and "Biko Tirol," to ensure high-quality, healthy, and conscious meat consumption. Their motto "From the region for the region" embodies their commitment to local sustainability and responsible farming practices.</p>	<p>According to Bioland requirements: Cattle for breeding and beef should have the possibility of free movement throughout the whole year. Cattle above 12 months shall have access to pasture during vegetation period. The min. grazing area is 600 m² per livestock unit during the total vegetation period. In case of extremely wet or dry conditions the grazing can be suspended for a short term. Inspections of animal husbandry quality are conducted using criteria related to both husbandry practices and product outcomes, assessing animal well-being and production quality. BIOLAND provides guidelines with key checkpoints and evaluation factors. Contractual operations are</p>	<p>Suckler cow husbandry: the calves suckle from their mother for 9 months.</p>
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						<p>inspected through a written questionnaire (operation report) and an annual on-site visit by an inspector. The visit results in an inspection report, and this process ensures compliance with BIOLAND's standards. Concentrate is only allowed for final fattening.</p>	
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<p>ANFOSC - Associazione Nazionale Formaggi sotto il cielo</p>	<p>2011</p>	<p>36, including some farms that do not produce milk but other types of high quality products (olive oil, wine, wheat, legumes, meat) under the product specification 'Me.No®'</p>	<p>Dairy</p>	<p>Expected benefits - High quality products for consumers; fair income for producers; improved animal welfare; environmental sustainability. Beneficiaries: consumers, farmers.</p>	<p>the goal of the Label is to produce high quality milk and dairy products, but also meat, improving the income of farmers and adopting sustainable production techniques: the product specification aims at producing milk or meat from animals fed with hay (if raised in barns) or in pastures (in grazing farms), rich in forage species (at least 6). A minimum number of concentrates is allowed. Silage, haylage and chemical weeding are not allowed. Animal and pasture production needs to be kept at sustainable levels, with the use of low production inputs, including water. Forage seeding is allowed only by sod-seeding. Organic fertilisation (mature manure) is required as a general rule. The optimal stage to harvest forage has been identified and a minimum rate of forage quality is set (70/100)</p>	<p>Not available</p>	<p>not available</p>
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Stichting Weidegang	2014	15771 in 2021	Dairy	More cows in the landscape; Higher prize for milk sold by dairies, grazing premium for the farmer	Encourage the visibility of cows in the Dutch landscape by supporting grazing. The cow in the pasture is a characteristic part of the Dutch landscape.	• Cows graze in the pasture for at least 120 days a year, at least six hours a day (or 720 hours per year in total with at least 120 grazing days), from spring to autumn.	none
Stichting Milieukeur	2018	>700	Dairy	The certified products are produced with respect for nature, climate, and the animals. Farmers receive a premium from some dairy industries if they are included in the program.	On the way to PlanetProof is a European sustainability label that proves more sustainable agricultural production. The label is available for arable crops, fruits and vegetables, milk, eggs, ornamentals (flowers, plants, trees, flower bulbs, etc.), and prepared and processed food products. Products with this quality label comply with strict environmental criteria related to 8 sustainability themes. Therefore, choosing certified products is good for the planet because the farmers and growers produce with respect for nature, climate, and the animals. The criteria and measures go beyond legal requirements.	*Cows graze for at least 120 days a year, at least six hours a day (or 720 hours per year in total with at least 120 grazing days); * young stock graze on average more than 100 days in their first two years	Max 10 cows/ha grazing platform; many additional requirements in the areas biodiversity, nutrient cycles, nature, climate, animal health and animal welfare (the grazing criteria fall in the category animal health and animal welfare)

Stichting Beter Leven keurmerk	2019	35	Dairy	Better life / welfare for dairy cows; some supermarkets provide additional income for farmers	The Better Life Label Foundation aims to contribute to demonstrably improving the animal welfare of farm animals.	*1, 2 and 3 stars: young stock graze on average more than 100 days in their first two years; * 1 star: dairy cows graze at least 120 days with six hours a day; * 2 stars: dairy cows graze 150 days, eight hours a day; *3 stars: cows graze 180 days, eight hours a day	* Area/cow in the stable, brushes in the stable, rubber or deep litter layer in cubicles, additional requirements for transport distance, nature, energy, climate, local feed and manure
Albert Heijn / Royal A-ware	2017	450	Dairy	More sustainable dairy products; additional income for farmers in the program	To produce increasingly sustainable dairy products, with a focus on animals, the environment and dairy farmers.	*Cows graze for at least 120 days a year, at least six hours a day (or 720 hours per year in total with at least 120 grazing days); grazing for at least six hours a day and 180 days is a best-effort obligation; * young stock graze at least 3 months between birth and their first calving.	Several fields: Better for the cow (meadow and barn, caring for cows, caring for calves), Better for nature (ground-based, climate, biodiversity, livestock feed), Better for the farmer (professionalism and safety, transparent)
Carne Barrosã PDO	1996		Meat and Meat products	The breed producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the meat and other meat products with a value add, and all the process of transformation,	The purpose of the Association is to promote, defend and sell the products from the Barroso Region, mainly beef (local breed) and honey. The cows have to be fed only with local products.	The cows have to be fed with local products, in extensive regimes	• Meat from local beef breed fed on natural pastures, coming from rural and mountain areas, raised in extensive regimes

				storage and marketing is the responsibility of the producer organisation			
Carnalentejana PDO	1992		Meat and Meat products	The breed producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the meat and other meat products with a value add, and all the process of transformation, storage and marketing is the responsibility of the producer organisation	The purpose of the Association is to promote, defend and sell the products from the local beef breed - Alentejana	The cows have to be raised in extensive regimes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meat from local beef breed, coming from rural areas, raised in extensive regimes
Carne Mertolenga PDO	1994		Meat and Meat products	The breed producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the meat and other meat products with a value add, and all the process of transformation, storage and marketing is the	The purpose of the Association is to promote, defend and sell the products from the local beef breed - Mertolenga	The cows have to be raised in extensive regimes, and fed with grass, hay or other forages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meat from local beef breed, coming from rural areas, raised in extensive regimes

				responsibility of the producer organisation			
TERRA NOSTRA Leite de Pastagem Vacas Felizes	2015		Dairy	The producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the milk with a value add	This programme promotes the differentiation of the Azorean milk, based on 5 pillars: grazing, animal welfare, quality and food safety, sustainable production and efficiency	• The cows have access to grassland 365 days per year	• Milk and dairy products from animals fed 365 days on natural pastures
UNILEITE Leite de Pastagem	1954		Dairy	The producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the milk with a value add	The products have their origin in a natural environment, where the cows grow, living all their lives in the grasslands	• The cows have access to grassland 365 days per year	• Milk and dairy products from animals fed 365 days on natural pastures
MILHAFRE Leite de Pastagem	2019		Dairy	The producers benefit from the label, so they can sell the milk with a value add	This brand bet on differentiation in the grassland production methods, animal welfare and environment care	• The cows have access to grassland 365 days per year	• Milk and dairy products from animals fed 365 days on natural pastures

<p>Asociația pentru promovarea produselor tradiționale de pe Valea Gurghiului</p>	<p>2016</p>		<p>Dairy</p>	<p>Group of farmers/ Value add chain</p>	<p>"- Preserve biodiversity by adapting management practices; - Reduce the inputs required for production; - Improving the conditions of the valorisation of cattle and their products, supporting producers of bovine products;"</p>	<p>"The production method developed locally consists in the processing of cow's milk harvested from dairy cows raised and fed in an extensive system on the seminatural meadows of the Gurghiului Valley. Dairy cows are fed only with green mass from the geographical area delimited by grazing in the summer, and in the winter with hay harvested from the hayfields in the specific geographical area."</p>	<p>The milk, the raw material, is obtained from cows reared in the defined geographical area. The production area consists of the administrative territory of the following communes: Ibănești, Hodac and Gurghiu and the belonging villages.</p>
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<p>Asociatia Producatorilor de Telemea de Sibiu</p>	<p>2018</p>		<p>Dairy</p>	<p>Group of farmers</p>	<p>"Cheese production and quality are closely linked to climatic, geological and vegetation conditions, which are essential for high quality dairy production. In this geographical environment, there is a specific historical and cultural element with local social roots, which is important for the characteristics of the product: it is the prehistoric small transhumance, which allows animals to take advantage of the mountain pastures in the area. Agroecological principles: preserving biodiversity by adapting management practices; reducing the inputs required for production"</p>	<p>"In Sibiu County, 60 types of meadows are grouped ecopratically. These are grouped into units (phytogeographical) and subunits (the main type - characteristic of meadows, with the difference in vegetation and production classes also determined by the subtypes of meadows). The animals whose milk is used are mainly grazed on pasture, with a minimum grazing period of 200-230 days/year depending on the weather (from April to November). On days when the sheep are unable to graze, they are fed with green fodder and unfermented hay from farms in the defined area."</p>	<p>The milk comes from animals reared in the defined geographical area: the main ridge of the Tarnava Mountains to the north, the main ridge of the Fagaras and Lotru Mountains to the south, the Hartibaci Plateau to the east and the Secaşelor-Valea Sebesului Plateau to the west.</p>
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<p>PRODUS MONTAN = Mountain Product</p>	<p>2016</p>		<p>Dairy & Meat and Meat products</p>	<p>Premium programme for the mountain industry</p>	<p>Preserve biodiversity by adapting management practices; .</p>	<p>"MONTAN PRODUCT - product intended for human consumption, in which case: - the raw materials, but also the fodder for the farm animals come mainly from the areas mountains; - in the case of processed products, the processing also takes place in mountainous areas. "</p>	<p>"To obtain this certification, the locality must be on the list of localities in the mountain area. The general delimitation criteria that were the basis for creating this list were: - average altitude between 350 and 500 m - altitude below 350 m and average slope greater than or equal to 20%."</p>
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<p>Asociația Producătorilor "Cașcavalul De Săveni"</p>	<p>2017</p>		<p>Dairy</p>	<p>Group of farmers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - adopting management practices that aim to improve animal health - reducing the inputs required for production -preserving biodiversity by adapting management practice 	<p>The characteristics of the milk are due to the hilly relief suitable for pastures and meadows with diversified flora: 50-60% grasses, 35-40% legumes and 5-10% fodder species from other families, which give a feed of a special quality. In this geographical area there is a forest-steppe vegetation. The meadows are cultivated with grasses from the fescue category. A large part of the meadows is degraded due to landslides and intensive grazing. On the salty lands, there is specific vegetation, with low plant mass that positively influences the quality of the milk. Pastures are rich in: red fescue, field grass, sedge, clover, etc. But also the invading bushes formed by juniper, blueberry,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The geographical area of origin of the milk is the northern half of Botoșani county. - Milk collection takes place from three categories of farms: small, medium and large. - Milking is done manually on small and medium farms, or automatically on large farms. - milk from pregnant cows one month before calving and 35 days after calving is not processed. - The freshly milked milk is transported in the shortest time (max. 2 hours) to the processing point and is processed immediately. - The milk is transported with the help of collection trucks
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						<p>raspberry, black grass and nettle. The representative species are: (Agropyron cristatum), (Stipa capillata), (Stipa lessingiana), (Festuca valesiaca), and on degraded lands there are associations (Poa bulbosa), (Cynodon dactylon), (Bromustectorum)</p>	
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Fidelio - Biosuisse	1994		Meat and Meat products			Pasture access in the summer.	Adherence to Bio Suisse guidelines. No use of chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizers. Limiting the number of animals based on farm's feed capacity. Purchasing of animals primarily from organic farms
Bio - Weide - Beef			Meat and Meat products			RAUS Guidelines: During summer, cattle must be on pasture for at least 26 days per month. In winter minimum 13 days per month of outdoor access. Additionally, there is a daily grazing requirement during the growing season (at least 8 hours).	Feeding with soy is prohibited. Each animal should have a minimum of 50% beef breed genetics (e.g. Limousin, Angus, Simmental).

KAG Freiland	1972		Dairy & Meat and Meat products			Group housing in open stables, daily pasture access in summer, and outdoor access in winter are mandatory. During the growing season, all animals over two weeks of age must have access to pasture. This applies to fattening calves as well. For calves weaned from milk, a minimum of three hours of pasture time per day is required.	Animals are allowed to be transported for a maximum of one hour or 30 kilometres before slaughter.
Natura-Beef	1980		Meat and Meat products			RAUS Guidelines: During summer cattle must be on pasture for at least 26 days per month. In winter minimum 13 days per month of outdoor access.	
Natura-Veal	2009	1600	Meat and Meat products			RAUS Guidelines: During summer cattle must be on pasture for at least 26 days per month. In winter minimum 13 days per month of outdoor access.	
De Yerba							

Swedish Pasture Beef and Lamb association	2004	45		Sigill owns the standard, which can be used by anyone. Possible expected financial benefits is however created in a market relation between buyer and seller.	All five but focused on preserving biodiversity on semi-natural grasslands by maintained management.	Minimum: 50 % of the grazing area is HNV semi-natural pastures, the animals are grazing there at least 50 % of the national stipulated grazing period, minimum 70 % roughage in winter feed rations, no non-certified soya in the concentrates.	Third party certification scheme with standard owned by Sigill and the criteria checked on farm by independent certification body every two year, self-check to be sent in every other year.
KRAV	1985		Dairy & Meat and Meat products	Added values, not the least for animal welfare, compared to non-organic production.		Prolonged grazing period compared to the compulsory grazing period in Sweden. Also grazing for young calves/lambs and adult intact bulls.	Plenty, but most important no mineral fertilizer and no pesticides.
Swedish government			Dairy & Meat and Meat products	Added values from Swedish production compared to imported products.		Grazing is compulsory by law for all ruminants in Sweden, except young calves/lambs and adult intact bulls. The label shown here is showing all steps in the production (not animal husbandry only) has been undertaken in Sweden.	Yes, 400-600 additional rules for ruminant production.
Haghultskossorna							

Consortium:

Contact:

Website

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